

Different Types of Tissues in Modern Science of Histology

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Abstract

Histology is a field of science focused on analysis of structure, development and function of cells and tissues of animals and plants. The study uses microscopy as its main tool of analysis. Histology includes the knowledge about microscopic structure of organs and also cytology and embryology. The science focused on histology of ill tissues and cells is called histopathology. It is a very important tool in analysis of anatomical pathology of morbid tissues, which appears in cancerous cells in animal or human body. Histology is essential for understanding and development of disciplines such as medicine, biology, veterinary medicine and many different sub-disciplines.

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Histology deals with the infinitesimal structure of tissues. Every organism consists of cells, and the cells are responsible for creating tissues. When taking animal organisms into consideration, four basic types of tissues can be enumerated: muscle tissue, nervous tissue, connective tissue and epithelial tissue. Apart from playing an important part in creating organisms, tissues also create subtypes which are even more specialised within the particular task. [1]

Muscle tissue is divided into three subtypes: striated muscle also called skeletal muscle, non-striated muscle and cardiac muscle, also known as semi-striated muscle. Tissue mainly consists of extended cells which are specialised in length changing process, which stands for contraction and relaxation and accompanying changes in tension. Skeletal muscles consist of long, cylindrical cells in the shape of stick, which are usually called muscle fibres. Striated muscles are under voluntary control of somatic nervous system, which makes them dependant on the will of action of an animal. The striated fibre has many nuclei which are localised in peripheral parts of cells. The main compound of cytoplasm of striated muscle cells are myofilaments, which are the main factor responsible for activating the contraction. Myofibrils have a form of little fibres which form parallel bundles. In between myofibrils cytosol with many mitochondria fills space between fibres. Only a few striated muscles are independent from conscious intervention, which are for example muscles of middle ear or certain cells of respiratory muscles. [2]

Cardiac muscle consists of parallel cells which form bundles, similarly as in striated muscles,

but heart cells have the singular or double nuclei localised in the centre of cytosol. Cells are connected by intercalated disks. The activity of cardiac tissue consists of repeated, automatic contractions independent of conscious influence. Electric impulses are produced by cells of the electrical conduction system of the heart. At the same time, the regulation of heart activity is executed by nervous system and hormones. [3]

Non-striated muscle tissue is controlled by autonomic nervous system and hormones, and is not dependent on animal's will. Its cells are long and fusiformed with singular centre localised nuclei, whose shape depends on physiological state of cells. During the contraction nuclei also contracts and curls up. Muscle cells of non-striated muscle tissue are also called myocytes. In many non-striated muscles the interstitial cells of Cajal are present and they are responsible for muscle stimulation through electric impulse production. [4]

A different type of tissue is called a nervous tissue and consists of neurons and glial cells. Neurons are composed of cell body and axons which connect neurons via specialized signalling pathways are called synapses. Their role is to connect neurons to neural network. The main function of neurons is to transmit, receive and process the information through chemical and electrical signals. They create the primary component of central nervous system, including brain and spinal cord, and also of the peripheral nervous system, which includes autonomic nervous system (independent of conscious activity) and somatic nervous system (dependant of conscious activity). Neurons and the neural networks are responsible for control and organisation of body functions. The

second component of nervous tissue is neuroglia, also called glial cells. These non-neuronal cells are maintaining the homeostasis (constant environment), provide support and protection for neurons, both in central and peripheral nervous system. Glial cells fulfil free space in between neurons and, at the same time, they function as specific scaffold for nervous cells. [5]

Connective tissue, as its name suggests, connects other tissues and provides the flow between cells, tissues and organs. It is found between other types of tissues in every part of the body. Connective tissue has three main functions, which are mechanical protection for other tissues and organs, being a kind of a support, which provides proper organisation of structures in a body, and a mean of transport of chemical substances, nutrients and metabolic products and, last but not least, the protection of the body against pathogens, such as bacteria, viruses and other foreign and potentially harmful substances and structures. Connective tissue consists of cells and rich extracellular matrix (EM). The presence of the EM is the main factor providing the communication between body structures. Connective tissue also contains numerous blood vessels. It is responsible for giving the organs their proper shape. Some cells are responsible for active body protection against dangerous factors, others produce protective substances. Connective tissue is subdivided into proper connective tissue and special connective tissue, including bone, cartilage, blood, adipose tissue and reticular connective tissue. Proper connective tissue consists of loose connective tissue and dense connective tissue. The second subtype is subdivided into another two subtypes: dense regular and dense irregular connective tissues. Connective tissues include lymphoid, elastic and fibrous connective tissues. Despite many different subtypes of connective tissues they still have mutual characteristics, which are widely spread cells in extracellular fluid. Furthermore, the ground substance is present in all types of connective tissues. Moreover, the matrix for connective tissues is composed of fibres and ground substance. [6,7]

The last type of four basic types of animal tissues is epithelial tissue. Its main mass consists of cells, when at the same extracellular matrix the mass is very scanty. These two properties make the epithelial a compact system of cells. In human body, epithelial cells take up to 60% of all cells. In organism between organs there is a lot of free space. To secure and separate organs and tissues from blood and interstitial fluid, epithelial tissue is responsible for covering structures and for organising transport between tissues and their extracellular environment. [8]

The basic types of animal tissues are components of organs and systems. Tissues cooperate with each other via signalling pathways and signalling

molecules to coordinate the reactions occurring in a body. [9]

Tissues from plants, microorganisms and fungi are also the subject of histological researches. Their structure is very different in comparison to animal structures. The main tissues characteristic for these organisms are dermal tissues, meristematic tissues, vascular tissues and ground tissues. [10]

Dermal tissue covers the surface of leaves, flowers roots and stems. It is one layer of cells, which protects the plant from negative influence of external environment. Meristematic tissue contains undifferentiated cells, which are responsible for plant's growth during its life time. Meristematic cells are present in various parts of a plant. Vascular tissue can be found in vascular plants and is formed by multiple kinds of cells. The primary components are phloem and xylem, which transport fluid and nutrients inside a plant. Furthermore, ground tissue includes all other tissues, which are not dermal or ground tissues. It fulfils most of the plant; they take part in photosynthesis, breathing osmosis but also accumulate spare substances. [11]

The organisation of the body from cell to system is a subject of interest of histology. All interactions have a special meaning about typical interactions and relations of technique adjustment, which makes the research easier, faster and cheaper at the same time. [12]

Immunocytochemistry is a method of selective identification of different substances through exploiting the principle (in some techniques also secondary) antibodies, which are specifically binding with antigens (proteins) in a tested section of tissue. These methods are a very important tool in the histological study. [13]

In the histological research, different kinds of preparation can be used for microscopic assessment. It can be pieces, swabs or prints of organs, whole amounts (in case of some parasites, like cestoda) and even cell cultures. Immuno-histochemical techniques are widely used in diagnosis of pathogenic cells found in cancerous tissues. The knowledge of cell cycle and its specific markers, which are genes and their products- enzymes and proteins- gives the opportunity of assessment of particular cell events, such as cell death, proliferation or analysis of metabolic pathways. Of course, immunohistochemistry is used also in case of basic research, which provides new information about cell biology and function of certain substances in the system, localization and distribution of biomarkers and for gene expression analysis, [14]

Antibodies used during staining procedure have to be tagged with specific substances, which make them visible during the visualisation after forming the complex antibody-antigen or make them possible to be detected and bonded by secondary antibody, which is also tagged and visualised during

detection. The method of visualisation depends on the type of used conjugated chemical. Antibodies can be conjugated with enzyme, which is usually peroxidase responsible for colour-producing reaction, which visualizes the product. Antibodies can also be tagged to fluorophore – fluorescent chemical compound, which can re-emit light at the certain length of wave, after light excitation. In this case, the complexes antibody-antigen is detected under the fluorescence microscope with fluorescent light. Other types of detection can be used for visualisation radioactive or biotin-tagged primary antibodies. [15]

As it was debrided earlier, the preparation of sections for staining procedure depends on purpose and type of studied tissues. Sections can be embedded in paraffin, epoxy resin or cryomedia in cryostat. In some cases, the epitopes may require additional steps, which make them available for used antigens. It may include paraffin removal and antigen retrieval. [16]

The procedures of increased availability of antigens are based on temperature, enzymatic method, chemical method or combination of temperature with enzymatic reaction. They eliminate the bonds formed during reactions between tissue and formalin, which makes the procedure of antigen identification possible. [17]

Next step is inhibition of endogenous proteins until the beginning of staining; this process prevents decaying and protects the desired cell production. Also, during immune-histochemical procedures obtained results seem to be very important. To prevent this process, the section after the procedure of preparation has to be incubated in buffer, which contains large biomolecules blocking sites, where primary and secondary antibodies could be bonded in non-specific way. [18]

In immunochemistry there are two types of antigens which are used. Monoclonal antibodies are produced by one clone of single cell of lymphocyte B. Polyclonal antibodies are produced by many cells, they are specific to certain type of protein, but can recognise different motifs, called epitopes. In addition, regardless the type of immunochemical strategy, primary and secondary antibodies can be used during the procedure. In the first case, primary antibodies are used for antigen detection and they are usually not labelled with a specific substance. Secondary, antibodies are used for visualisation of primary antibody antigen complexes. Secondary antibodies are conjugated with tags. In some cases only primary antibodies are used for product detection. In this case, every antibody has to be labelled. However, this method is less specific and it is more possible to obtain less valuable results. [19]

As Coleman (2009) suggested, histology is a branch of knowledge which covers the techniques of visualisation of processes and changes occurring in a body. Another important field of research is

pathology. Histopathology is a microscopic study of pathological changes in a body, which can manifest disease or activity of toxic factors. In clinical or toxicological study, histopathology is used for examination of specimen obtained after biopsy or operation. The main focus is to put on specific changes, which are characteristic for necrosis (unnatural cell death), cancerous transformation, changes in tissue structure etc. All these symptoms of different diseases are well seen under the microscope and only this method enables proper identification and verification of suspected pathology. Moreover, histopathology plays the main role in diagnosis of cancer, when the stage of cancer has to be recognized in order to apply the most effective treatment to a patient. [20]

In the field of toxicology, histology is needed in proper assessment of the influence on a body. In natural environment some organisms are present which can be used as bio indicators. Their specific reaction to certain substances in different concentrations results in characteristic changes in their anatomy and morphology. This makes them the perfect model for identification of environmental pollution, which can be verified during microscopic examination. Furthermore, histology is an absolute must during the clinical research, during which the safety of new medicine has to be tested on cell cultures, small animals and finally on human beings. During each stage, the interactions between a medicine and a living organism are verified, also with the use of histological observation. The same procedure takes place during safety assessment of cosmetic products. Each product used different substances on the surface of the body, which can interact with tissues in undesirable ways.

To sum up, histology is a very complex study, which unites chemical, technical and anatomical knowledge. The knowledge itself is not enough for proper assessment. Only practice and experience gives the certitude of a proper analysis. Although certain types of cells and tissues have the same properties, through their biological and genetic development, histology is very difficult, because of diversity of organisms and cases. Pathological changes, however, especially those of cancerous origin, can vary between two different organisms, which is a result of genetic instability of cancerous tissues. Nevertheless, histology is a still developing branch of knowledge. With technological development, the analysis of histological changes will become faster and more effective in the future. Microscopic assessment will still be a necessary element of every biological research, because it enables looking deeply inside, which is impossible to the naked human eye.

References:

1. Pratt R.L. Are we throwing histology out with the microscope? A look at histology from the physician's perspective. *AnatSciEduc*, 2009; 2:205–209.
2. Krathwohl D.R. A revision of Bloom's taxonomy: An overview. *Theory Pract*, 2002; 41:212–218.
3. Ferguson C. Using the revised taxonomy to plan and deliver team taught integrated, thematic units. *Theory Pract*, 2002; 41:238–243.
4. Drake R.L., McBride J.M., Lachman N., Pawlina W. Medical education in the anatomical sciences: The winds of change continue to blow. *AnatSciEduc*, 2009; 2:253–259.
5. Cotter J.R. Laboratory instruction in histology at the University of Buffalo: Recent replacement of microscope exercises with computer applications. *Anat Rec*, 2001, 265:212–221.
6. Krippendorf B.B., Lough J. Complete and rapid switch from light microscopy to virtual microscopy for teaching medical histology. *Anat Rec*, 2005; 285B:19–25.
7. Bloodgood R.A. *The use of microscopic images in medical education*. In: Gu J, Ogilvie RW (Editors). *Virtual Microscopy and Virtual Slides in Teaching, Diagnosis and Research*. 1st Ed. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 2005; 111–140.
8. <http://www.aperio.com/pathology-services/scanscope-CS-system-slides.asp> [available 13 April 2018].
9. Shaw P.A., Friedman E.S. Clinico-histologic conferences: Histology and disease. *AnatSciEduc*, 2012; 5:55–61.
10. Scoville S.A., Buskirk T.D. Traditional and virtual microscopy compared experimentally in a classroom setting. *ClinAnat*, 2007; 20:565–570.
11. Blake C.A., Lavoie H.A., Millette C.F. Teaching medical histology at the University of South Carolina School of Medicine: Transition to virtual slides and virtual microscopes. *Anat Rec*, 2003; 275B:196–206.
12. Bloodgood R.A., Ogilvie R.W. Trends in histology laboratory teaching in United States medical schools. *Anat Rec*, 2006; 289B:169–175.
13. Mescher A. *Junqueira's Basic Histology: Text and Atlas*. 12th Ed. Columbus, OH: McGraw-Hill Companies Inc, 2009; 480.
14. Coleman R. Can histology and pathology be taught without microscopes? The advantages and disadvantages of virtual histology. *Acta Histochem*, 2009; 111:1–4.
15. Amerongen H. Reordering histology to enhance engagement. *AnatSciEduc*, 2011; 4:176–177.
16. Feeback, D.L.. *Histology*. Springer-Verlag New York Inc, 1987;
17. Aperio. *ScanScope1 CS System*. Aperio Technologies, Inc., Vista, CA, 2009;
18. Bloodgood R.A. *Medical education without medical educators*. *MedEduc*, 2010; 44:630–632.
19. Heidger P.M.Jr., Dee F., Consoer D., Leaven T., Duncan J., Kreiter C. *Integrated approach to teaching and testing in histology with real and virtual imaging*. *Anat Rec*, 2002; 269:107–112.
20. Coleman P.. Quantitative and qualitative changes in teaching histology by means of virtual microscopy in an introductory course in human anatomy, 2009; [in *Anatomical Science Education*: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ase.105>] [available 15 April 2018].

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest